

Spontaneous Rupture of an Unscarred Uterus in a Woman at 35 Weeks of Pregnancy with Abdominal Pain: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

A spontaneous rupture of the unscarred uterus in a primigravid patient is extremely rare and is associated with high perinatal and maternal morbidity and mortality.

A 34-year-old white primigravid woman, 35 weeks of gestation, presented with sudden onset of acute abdomen. An emergency laparotomy was performed, and a uterine rupture was found as the cause of the event.

A rupture of the pregnant uterus should always be considered in a pregnant woman presenting with abdominal pain, even in a primigravid patient.

BACKGROUND

Rupture of the pregnant uterus is an uncommon but severe obstetrical event, which is associated with high perinatal and maternal morbidity and mortality. It occurs mostly secondary to a previous caesarean section the “scarred uterus”), making this its main risk factor with an incidence of around 1%. Rupture in a primigravid patient is extremely rare and, in most cases, totally unexpected. The incidence of uterus rupture in general (primigravid or multigravida) is significantly higher in developing countries than in developed countries. It is caused by worse antenatal and obstetric care (such as prolonged or obstructed labor, high frequency of home deliveries with prolonged labor, grand multiparity, shortened inter-delivery interval, gestational age greater than 40 weeks, and a birth weight greater than 4000 gm. Symptoms of uterine rupture are severe abdominal pain of sudden onset, palpable fetal body parts, cessation of contractions, signs of intraperitoneal bleeding, and all the features correlated to the hemorrhage that could lead to maternal and fetal (fetal distress, bradycardia) deterioration of vital signs leading up to shock. Less common symptoms are epigastric pain, shoulder pain (right sided or bilateral), abdominal distension and paralytic ileus, hematuria, hypertonic uterus, altered uterine contour.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 34-year-primigravida woman at 35 weeks of pregnancy presented to the hospital with unclear persistent abdominopelvic pain for 8 hours, radiating from the left side to the whole abdomen. The patient had no medical, surgical, or gynecologic history. The current pregnancy was without any relevant finding apart from uterine didelphys. At admission, the patient was afebrile, tachycardic and normotensive. The patient was exhibited pallor, an excessive increase in pulse rate, and exacerbating of abdominal pain. The abdominal palpation was globally painful tender without any contraction. Fetal monitoring showed an abrupt severe fetal heart rate deceleration with no uterine contractions. The laboratory and urinary values were nonspecific. Sonographic examination found no evidence of placental abruption or uterine rupture. The fetus was in cephalic position with a normal fetal cardiac activity and normal liquor. The maternal abdomen examination was tender in the fundal area. Having acute onset of abdominal pain and presence fetal heart deceleration on CTG, we decided to proceed with Category 1 caesarean section. An emergency caesarean delivery was then performed under general anesthesia.

On accessing the abdominal cavity, we found a hemoperitoneum of 1.5 L. After delivering a 2655-g neonate by transverse incision, we identified 3 cm tear in the fundus wall of the uterus. The rupture was sutured by separate X-stitches with absorbable sutures. Uterus was atonic. Decision was made for B lynch suture application. Careful examination of the rest of the cavity revealed no other signs of rupture. In total, the patient lost 1500 mL of blood and was transfused with 2 units of blood.

The postoperative outcome was favorable, and the mother and infant were able to leave the maternity ward after 6 days. Analysis of the placenta did not reveal any pathology.

DISCUSSION

Spontaneous uterine rupture is a rare life-threatening obstetrical complication. It usually occurs during labor after a previous caesarean delivery or any previous uterine procedures such as myomectomy or any other surgical intervention.

The diagnosis of uterine rupture relies on cardiotocographic abnormalities and unexplained and unusual abdominal pain, which was also observed in our patient case. Retrospectively, the only potential risk factor of this patient was uterine anomaly uterus didelphys.

Extreme caution should be taken when managing a patient with a previous uterine scar and attempting a trial of labour. Increased accessibility to good obstetric care and prompt referral system to equipped facilities with availability of transportation services is essential for developing countries to avoid these catastrophic emergencies. Uterine rupture should be considered in the differential diagnosis in all pregnant patients who present with acute abdomen, show fluid collection in the peritoneal cavity, and have specific risks factors. Treatment of uterine rupture is an early surgical intervention and previous hemodynamic stabilization of the patient where possible. It is possible to reduce foetal and maternal mortality with a prompt intervention, less than 18 minutes from onset of prolonged deceleration to delivery.

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